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PROJECT FoRWaRD: Facets of Recognizing Words and Reading Discernment — Basis for Strengthening Reading Levels among Key Stage 1 Learners

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Introduction

Reading is a vital foundation of lifelong learning and academic success. To address literacy gaps from the pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd), through DepEd Order No. 34, s. 2022, implemented the Learning Recovery Plan (LRP). In support, Sto. Toribio Elementary School launched **Project FoRWaRD** (Facets of Recognizing Words and Reading Discernment), a reading intervention to improve literacy among struggling learners. PHIL-IRI results for SY 2022–2023 showed forty-five (45) Key Stage 1 learners from Grades 1–3 at the frustration level in English and Filipino. The project aimed to strengthen word recognition, fluency, and comprehension through guided sessions aligned with DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019, promoting reading proficiency and a culture of literacy.

Reading comprehension and word recognition are essential skills influencing all areas of learning. In line with DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2015, under the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program, Project FoRWaRD supports the “Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa” advocacy that envisions every Filipino child as a reader. Through structured reading activities, it addresses decoding and comprehension challenges, helping learners progress from word recognition to reading discernment. The study aimed to determine learners’ perceptions, assess their reading levels, and compare PHIL-IRI results before and after intervention.

Method

A mixed-method design was used, combining pre- and post-test results with teacher and parent interviews. After securing required permissions and consent, the FoRWaRD intervention focused on improving word recognition, fluency, and comprehension through one-on-one and small-group sessions. The PHIL-IRI Post-Assessment measured learners’ progress, supported by qualitative insights on engagement and motivation.

Results

Project FoRWaRD created a supportive reading environment where learners became more participative and confident. Teachers observed notable improvement in decoding, vocabulary, and comprehension. The PHIL-IRI Post-Assessment indicated significant progress: 77.78% accurately recognized letter sounds, 83.87% decoded Filipino words, 85.29% improved oral reading, 78.57% understood words in context, and 75.56% demonstrated better comprehension. Many learners advanced from frustration to instructional or independent reading levels. Teachers and parents reported greater enthusiasm and consistent reading practice at home.

Discussion and Conclusion

Findings show that Project FoRWaRD effectively improved learners’ literacy and engagement. By focusing on foundational reading components, the program addressed early literacy gaps and enhanced comprehension and confidence. Structured questioning and reflective discussions

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fostered metacognitive awareness, helping learners understand texts more deeply. The study supports DepEd's National Learning Recovery Plan (DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023) by showing that consistent, teacher-led interventions close learning gaps and nurture a reading culture. Project FoRWaRD proves that focused reading support transforms struggling readers into independent, motivated learners.

References

DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2015 – *Guidelines on the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program*.
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